

Fitbit Freedom: Raspberry Pi Local Server for Fitbit Data

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Fitbit Charge 6

Regular user

Engineer

- Image of the health and fitness section is screenshot of https://store.google.com/us/product/fitbit_charge_6?hl=en-US taken by the Author, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Image of the Fitbit Charge 6 usage overview is generated in <https://app.diagrams.net/> application, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Fitbit Charge 6

Memory

Saves 7 days of detailed motion data, minute by minute
Saves daily totals for the last 30 days
Stores heart rate data at 1 second intervals during exercise tracking and at 5 second intervals all other times

Sensors and components

- Optical heart rate monitor
- 3-axis accelerometer
- Built-in GPS + GLONASS
- Red and infrared sensors for oxygen saturation (SpO2) monitoring. *Not available in all countries. Not intended to diagnose or treat any medical condition or for any other medical purpose. Intended to help you manage your well-being and keep track of your information. Requires more frequent charging.*
- Device temperature sensor (skin temperature variation available in the Fitbit app). *Only available in the Fitbit app and only displays variation. Not available in all markets. Not intended for medical purposes. Significant changes in ambient temperature may negatively impact skin temperature tracking.*
- Vibration motor
- Ambient light sensor
- NFC
- Multipurpose electrical sensors compatible with ECG app & EDA Scan app

What is inside?

□ Image of the documentation is screenshot taken by the Author of https://store.google.com/us/product/fitbit_charge_6_specs?hl=en-US – memory and sensors and components section, accessed on 9. May 2026.

□ Image of the Fitbit Charge 6 is taken by the Author.

Fitbit Charge 6

What data can be accessed and how?

What data is stored on Fitbit server?

- Image of the Fitbit Charge 6 is taken by the Author.
- Image of the Fitbit application is screenshot of the Android Fitbit application, taken by the Author.
- Image of the Fitbit communication infrastructure is generated in <https://app.diagrams.net/> application, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Fitbit Charge 6

Fitbit Charge 6

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

- Estimated step count & distance
- Activity type recognition
- Cardio fitness estimate (VO₂Max)

□ All images are screenshots taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.

Fitbit Charge 6

SLEEP TRACKING

- Sleep onset & wake detection
- Sleep stage recognition
- Sleep quality score

□ All images are screenshots taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.

Fitbit Charge 6

STRESS ASSESSMENT

- **Stress management score**
- **Mindfulness / meditation intervals**
- **Electrodermal Activity Scan (EDA)**

- All images of the application are screenshots taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.
- Image of the Fitbit Charge 6 is taken by the Author.

Fitbit Charge 6

HEALTH & PHYSIOLOGY

- Real-time heart rate
- Breathing rate estimate (BR)
- Blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂)
- Resting heart rate (RHR)
- Heart Rate Variability (HRV)
- Skin temperature variations

□ All images are screenshots taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.

Fitbit Charge 6

15:48 22

Health metrics

Dec 25, 2025

4 of 4 Metrics available

- 1 Breathing rate (BR) 17 bpm Personal range unavailable
- 2 Blood oxygen (SpO2) No data Feature unavailable
- 3 Resting heart rate (RHR) 67 bpm
- 4 Heart rate variability (HRV) 52 ms Personal range unavailable
- 5 Skin temp variation +0,7 °F

15:48 22

Breathing rate

Week Month Year

Dec 21 - 27, 2025

Personal range unavailable

20
17
14

S M T W T F S

Personal range In range Out of range

About breathing rate Learn more

Breathing rate (BR) is the number of breaths you take per minute. Your body adjusts your BR to eliminate carbon dioxide from the blood an...

15:48 22

Blood oxygen

Week Month Year

Dec 21 - 27, 2025

Personal range unavailable

100
90

S M T W T F S

Personal range In range Out of range

This feature is unavailable

Blood oxygen isn't supported in your location. You can see and delete existing data, but new data won't be collected.

Learn more

15:48 22

Resting heart rate

Week Month Year

Dec 21 - 27, 2025

70 bpm (avg)

Your personal range was 60 to 86 bpm this period

90
74
58

S M T W T F S

Personal range In range Out of range

About resting heart rate Learn more

Resting heart rate (RHR) is the number of times your heart beats per minute when you are still

15:49 22

Heart rate variability

Week Month Year

Dec 21 - 27, 2025

45 ms (avg)

Personal range unavailable

55
47
39

S M T W T F S

Personal range In range Out of range

About heart rate variability Learn more

Heart rate variability is the fluctuation of time (milliseconds) between your heartbeats. Even

15:49 22

Skin temp variation

Week Month Year

Dec 21 - 27, 2025

+0,7 °F (avg)

All in personal range

2.0
0
-2.0

S M T W T F S

Personal range In range Out of range

About skin temp variation Learn more

Skin temperature variation is the fluctuation in temperature taken from your wrist while you

Fitbit Charge 6

- Image of the Fitbit dashboard is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://www.fitbit.com/settings/profile> personal info section, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Image of the countries/regions where Fitbit ECG app is available is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://support.google.com/fitbit/answer/14236718?hl=en#zippy=%2Cwhat-countriesregions-is-the-fitbit-ecg-app-available-in>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Image of the Fitbit application is screenshot taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.

Fitbit Charge 6

Miloš Milošević
View Profile

DEVICES
View All Your Devices

Charge 6
View Device Settings

SETTINGS

- Personal Info
- Notifications
- Privacy
- Data Export
- Manage Data
- Manage Account Access
- Applications
- Help

Logout

Personal Info

Change Profile Picture

Change Cover Image

EMAIL ADDRESS
000milošević000@gmail.com
Change Personal Info

NAME
Miloš Milošević

SEX
Male

BIRTHDAY
2001 November 23

COUNTRY
United States

STATE
California

+ A lot of things... =

- Image of the Fitbit dashboard is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://www.fitbit.com/settings/profile> personal info section, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Image of the Fitbit Charge 6 is taken by the Author.
- Image of the Fitbit application is screenshot taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.

A lot of things... =

Fitbit Charge 6

Change Fitbit Account location

Change Google Account location

Reinstall the application

Do not allow location data

Restart the phone

Are you sure?

Without location data, exercise tracking, weather and other features will not work as expected on your Fitbit device.

TRY AGAIN

ALLOW LATER

- ❑ Images of the Fitbit application are screenshots taken by the Author from the Android Fitbit application.
- ❑ Images of the Fitbit Charge 6 is taken by the Author.

This was experimental setup with limitations.

Fitbit Charge 6

● Heart Rate <i>Only via Web API – not in mobile app or bulk export</i>	1-min / 1-sec intervals
● Sleep Stages <i>Only via Web API – not in mobile app or bulk export</i>	1-min intervals
● Activity / Steps <i>Broadly accessible; bulk export also available</i>	Daily summaries + intraday
● ECG <i>Not available in Serbia – geographic restriction applies</i>	Full waveform
● SpO₂ <i>Not available in Serbia – geographic restriction applies</i>	Daily estimates
● Raw PPG Signal <i>Not accessible via any interface; processed only on-device</i>	

Let's talk!

- 1** Were you aware that some Fitbit features and data access are limited by country or device?
- 2** Would you still buy a wearable device if you knew about these limitations?
- 3** What would you use Fitbit Web API data (*e.g.*, intraday heart rate and steps) for?

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Read API Docs

Fitbit Logos
Download our logos and read trademark guidelines and terms of service

Download All

Get affiliated
Become a Fitbit Affiliate and make money from your users who buy a Fitbit.

Learn more

Applications I registered

+ Register a new app

Application Testing app

This app will be used only for testing purposes.

Edit Application Settings Delete Application

Reset Client Secret Revoke Client Access Tokens

OAuth 2.0 Client ID
23TNKK

Client Secret
db6ba90ffb3b84439c60bde03c956146

Redirect URL
http://localhost:3000/callback

OAuth 2.0: Authorization URI
https://www.fitbit.com/oauth2/authorize

OAuth 2.0: Access/Refresh Token Request URI
https://api.fitbit.com/oauth2/token

[OAuth 2.0 Tutorial](#)

- 1 Register App**
Get Client ID & Client Secret from dev.fitbit.com
- 2 User Login**
User authenticates via Fitbit (browser redirect)
- 3 Grant Scope**
User explicitly approves data categories
- 4 Access Token**
Server returns short-lived access token
- 5 API Calls**
Bearer token used in HTTPS requests to Web API
- 6 Refresh Token**
Renewed without user interaction when token expires

Image of the Fitbit application for Web API is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://dev.fitbit.com/apps>, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Register an application

New API is available, but not stable yet...

Important update:
The Fitbit Web APIs are moving to a new, scalable infrastructure. We will be deprecating the legacy Fitbit Web API in September 2026. Registration of new applications via this form is discontinued. To register a new application, please use the new process on the [Google Health API developer site](#).

Application Name *

Description *

Application Website URL *

Start your migration or new app development today!
To ensure a seamless experience for your users, we recommend waiting until the end of May 2026 to officially launch your integration to align with legacy Fitbit account deprecation. Please be aware that from now until the end of May, breaking changes may occur as we respond to developer feedback.

Migration guide

The Google Health API is a new API built from the ground up allowing developers to query Fitbit user data. This is not just an update, it's a strategic move to ensure your apps are secure, reliable, and ready for future advancements in health technology. The API supports a new console for registering your apps, Google OAuth 2.0 support, new data types, new endpoint schema, and new response format.

The guide is designed to help developers migrate their existing Fitbit Web API apps to the new Google Health API.

Welcome to the Google Health API

The Google Health API is the next generation of the Fitbit Web API. It lets you view and manage health and fitness metrics and measurement data from Fitbit, Pixel Watch, and other third-party devices and apps – all on a unified API infrastructure on Google's secure OAuth 2.0 framework.

- Standardization and new features**
Simplified data type bundles, standardized formats, auto-subscribing webhooks, HTTP and gRPC protocols, reconciled stream of data from all sources, and more
- Scalability**
Designed to meet data demands and support a comprehensive set of health and fitness data, serving as a backbone of the next generation of AI-driven health and fitness apps
- Improved identity management**
Utilizes Google OAuth 2.0 libraries for authentication, simplifying the identity management process

[Get Started](#) [Migrate from the Fitbit Web API](#)

- Image of the Fitbit register an application tab for Web API is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://dev.fitbit.com/apps/new>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Image of the Fitbit migration guide for Web API is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://developers.google.com/health/migration>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Image of the Welcome page for Google Health API is screenshot taken by the Author from the <https://developers.google.com/health>, accessed on 9. May 2026.

New application is also available...

□ Images of the Google Health application are screenshots taken by the Author on 18. June 2026.

Let's demonstrate!

1 Fitbit Web API overview

2 Fitbit Web API migration

- Fitbit Web API link is <https://dev.fitbit.com/apps/new>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Fitbit Web API migration setup link is <https://developers.google.com/health/migration>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Fitbit Web API endpoints documentation link is <https://dev.fitbit.com/build/reference/web-api/>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsVfQy1KGJ4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

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Freedom: Idea of Local Server

- Wearable devices function as a “human black box” that records large amounts of personal data (Fereidooni et al., 2017).
- This raises concerns about control and accessibility of collected health data.
- Inspired by the workshop “Evolution of the Telephone Answering Machine – Home Server” by professor Predrag Pejović at PSSOH 2021 Conference.
- The workshop presented the concept of building a personal home server with a Raspberry Pi.

- Fereidooni et al., 2017. - Fitness Trackers: Fit for Health but Unfit for Security and Privacy https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319169359_Fitness_Trackers_Fit_for_Health_but_Unfit_for_Security_and_Privacy, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Pejović Predrag – Evolution of the Telephone Answering Machine – Home Server <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5546525>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Pejović Predrag – PSSOH 2021: Home Server Presentation <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r0J91yKURDU>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Pejović Predrag – PSSOH 2021: Ubuntu Setup Tutorial <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sTyRZpNgS54>, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Informacije o Uređaju

Svi bežični uređaji konektovani na ruter će biti prikazani ovde, uključujući ime uređaja i MAC adresu

Bežični Pristupni Uređaj

Br.	Ime Hosta	MAC Adresa	IP Adresa	Tip adrese	station_connected_node	Operacija
1	--	C0 [redacted] 10	192.168.0.6	DHCP	5G	Blokiraj
2	DESKTOP-317DVK0	00 [redacted] D5	192.168.0.4	DHCP	5G	Blokiraj
3	raspberry	B8 [redacted] 16	192.168.0.8	static	2.4G	Blokiraj

Kablovski Pristupni Uređaj

Br.	Ime Hosta	MAC Adresa	IP Adresa	Tip adrese
1	DESKTOP-VLTKIVC	A8 [redacted] 9	192.168.0.3	DHCP

□ Image is screenshot taken by the Author - WireGuard application welcome screen - <https://www.wireguard.com/>, accessed on 9. May 2026 .

Diagram for custom integration...

L E G E N D
 SRC.P/DST.P - Source/Destination port
 SRC.IP/DST.IP - Source/Destination address
 {L_IP} - Laptop IP address
 {L_WG_IP} - Laptop WireGuard IP address
 {R_IP} - Raspberry Pi IP address
 {R_WG_IP} - Raspberry Pi WireGuard IP address
 {R_WG_P} - Raspberry Pi WireGuard listening port
 {APP_P} - Application port
 {APP_REQ} - Application request
 {API_REQ} - API request for Fitbit server
 {WEB_API} - Address of Fitbit Web API
 {PUB_IP} - Public IP address for router
 {HTTPS_P} - HTTPS Port
 {EPi, i={1,2,3,4}} - Ephemeral port
 ———> Outgoing traffic - - - - -> Incoming traffic

□ Diagram is generated in <https://app.diagrams.net/> application, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Let's talk!

1 Would you consider building your own personal server for health data (e.g. Raspberry Pi-based)?

2 Are you familiar with static IP address services available in Serbia?

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Let's demonstrate!

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Raspberry Pi OS & server installation

2

Router & WireGuard configuration

3

Preparing for application development

- ❑ Raspberry Pi Imager software is available on <https://www.raspberrypi.com/software/>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- ❑ WireGuard VPN software is available on <https://www.wireguard.com/>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- ❑ PDF document with server installation and web service configuration is available on https://drive.google.com/file/d/1g97t6wh6Qp6H5LNfuxTPvdIOEOWcmNjx/view?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- ❑ All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsVfOy1KGJ4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

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System Architecture

Oauth2.0 Authentication Flow

Authentication - User consent

Testing app by **Testing** would like the ability to access the following data in your account

Warning! This app is not using HTTPS to securely obtain your permission.

- Allow All
- electrocardiogram
- sleep
- heart rate
- oxygen saturation (SpO2)

If you allow only some of this data, Testing app may not function as intended. [Learn more about these permissions here.](#)

Deny

Allow

The data you share with Testing app will be governed by Testing's [Privacy Policy](#) and [Terms of Service](#). You can always see or remove access in your [account settings](#).

Signed in as 000milosevic000@gmail.com
[Not you?](#)

localhost:3000/callback?code=a042cd6f4506269586d6682e3c9d7d679643a193#_=_

10.8.0.1:3000/callback?code=a042cd6f4506269586d6682e3c9d7d679643a193#_=_

Not secure 10.8.0.1:3000/callback?code=a042cd6f4506269586d6682e3c9d7d679643a193#_=_

- Image of the Fitbit Web API Deny/Allow popup is screenshot of taken by the Author during the initial /auth request.
- Images of URI fields are the screenshots taken by the Author during the initial /auth request.

Let's demonstrate!

1 Application code overview

2 How to access & continue developing on the board?

3 How application looks like?

- Full application code is available on https://github.com/milosmilosmilos/fitbit_app.git, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Fitbit Google Health API endpoints specification link is <https://developers.google.com/health/endpoints>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- Fitbit Web API endpoints documentation link is <https://dev.fitbit.com/build/reference/web-api/>, accessed on 9. May 2026.
- All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsVfQy1KGI4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

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Fitbit Web API

Heart Rate ▾ Date: 12/25/2025 ▾ Intraday: 1 min ▾ Fetch Download JSON

#	timestamp	value
0	00:00:00	62
1	00:01:00	61
2	00:02:00	62
3	00:03:00	62
4	00:04:00	64
5	00:05:00	62
6	00:06:00	64
7	00:07:00	64
8	00:08:00	64
9	00:09:00	64
10	00:10:00	63
11	00:11:00	64
12	00:12:00	62
13	00:13:00	64
14	00:14:00	66
15	00:15:00	65
16	00:16:00	65
17	00:17:00	73
18	00:18:00	67
19	00:19:00	66
20	00:20:00	65
21	00:21:00	65

```

1  {
2    "activities-heart": [
3      {
4        "value": {
5          "customHeartRateZones": [],
6          "heartRateZones": [
7            {
13           ...
14         },
15         {
16           "caloriesOut": 0,
17           "max": 143,
18           "min": 119,
19           "minutes": 0,
20           "name": "Fat Burn"
21         },
22         {
23           "caloriesOut": 0,
24           "max": 175,
25           "min": 144,
26           "minutes": 0,
27           "name": "Cardio"
28         },
29         {
30           "caloriesOut": 0,
31           "max": 220,
32           "min": 176,
33           "minutes": 0,
34           "name": "Peak"
35         }
36       ],
37       "restingHeartRate": 68
38     },
39     "dateTime": "2025-12-25"
40   ],

```

```

41   ],
42   "activities-heart-intraday": {
43     "dataset": [
44       {
45         "time": "00:00:00",
46         "value": 62
47       },
48       {
49         "time": "00:01:00",
50         "value": 61
51       },
52       {
53         "time": "00:02:00",
54         "value": 62
55       },
56       {
57         "time": "00:03:00",
58         "value": 62
59       },
60       {
61         "time": "00:04:00",
62         "value": 64
63       },
64       {
65         "time": "00:05:00",
66         "value": 62
67       },
68       {
69         "time": "00:06:00",
70         "value": 64

```

- Images of the heart rate statistics are screenshots taken by the Author by applying filters: date: 12/25/2025, intraday: 1 min.
- All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsvfOy1KGJ4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Fitbit Web API

Heart Rate ▾ Date: 12/25/2025 ☰ Intraday: 1 sec ▾ Fetch Download JSON

#	timestamp	value
0	00:00:02	62
1	00:00:05	62
2	00:00:08	62
3	00:00:09	61
4	00:00:12	61
5	00:00:13	60
6	00:00:16	60
7	00:00:18	61
8	00:00:21	61
9	00:00:22	62
10	00:00:25	62
11	00:00:26	61
12	00:00:29	61
13	00:00:30	62
14	00:00:32	62
15	00:00:34	64
16	00:00:37	64
17	00:00:40	64
18	00:00:43	64
19	00:00:45	63
20	00:00:48	63

```

1  {
2  "activities-heart": [
3  {
4    "value": {
5      "customHeartRateZones": [],
6      "heartRateZones": [
7        {
8          "caloriesOut": 2221.8872000000115,
9          "max": 118,
10         "min": 30,
11         "minutes": 1440,
12         "name": "Out of Range"
13       },
14       {
15         "caloriesOut": 0,
16         "max": 143,
17         "min": 119,
18         "minutes": 0,
19         "name": "Fat Burn"
20       },
21       {
22         "caloriesOut": 0,
23         "max": 175,
24         "min": 144,
25         "minutes": 0,
26         "name": "Cardio"
27       },
28       {
29         "caloriesOut": 0,
30         "max": 220,
31         "min": 176,
32         "minutes": 0,
33         "name": "Peak"
34       }
35     ],
36     "restingHeartRate": 68
37   }

```

```

41 "activities-heart-intraday": {
42   "dataset": [
43     {
44       "time": "00:00:02",
45       "value": 62
46     },
47     {
48       "time": "00:00:05",
49       "value": 62
50     },
51     {
52       "time": "00:00:08",
53       "value": 62
54     },
55     {
56       "time": "00:00:09",
57       "value": 61
58     },
59     {
60       "time": "00:00:12",
61       "value": 61
62     },
63     {
64       "time": "00:00:13",
65       "value": 60
66     },
67     {
68       "time": "00:00:16",
69       "value": 60
70     },
71     {
72       "time": "00:00:18",
73       "value": 61
74     }

```

- ▢ Images of the heart rate statistics are screenshots taken by the Author by applying filters: date: 12/25/2025, intraday: 1 sec.
- ▢ All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsvfOy1KGJ4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

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Sleep Date:

#	timestamp	value
0	sleep	[{"dateOfSleep": "2025-12-25", "duration": 21900000, "efficiency": 82, "startTime": "2025-12-24T23:04:00.000", "endTime": "2025-12-25T05:09:00.000", "infoCode": 0, "isMainSleep": true, "levels": [{"dateTime": "2025-12-24T23:04:00.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 2640}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-24T23:48:00.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 930}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T00:03:30.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 210}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T00:36:30.000", "level": "deep", "seconds": 30}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T00:37:00.000", "level": "deep", "seconds": 210}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T00:42:00.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 1950}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:14:30.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 30}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:16:30.000", "level": "deep", "seconds": 30}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:17:00.000", "level": "deep", "seconds": 120}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:20:00.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 120}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:22:00.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 840}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:48:00.000", "level": "rem", "seconds": 900}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T02:03:00.000", "level": "rem", "seconds": 1950}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T03:50:30.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 750}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T04:03:00.000", "level": "light", "seconds": 1200}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T04:26:30.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 270}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T04:31:00.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 30}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T01:52:30.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 90}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T02:02:00.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 60}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T02:39:30.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 120}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T02:58:30.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 90}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T03:11:00.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 30}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T03:45:30.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 60}, {"dateTime": "2025-12-25T05:07:30.000", "level": "wake", "seconds": 90}], "summary": {"deep": {"count": 7, "minutes": 49}, "light": {"count": 19, "minutes": 207}, "thirtyDayAvgMinutes": 244, "rem": {"count": 4, "minutes": 44}, "thirtyDayAvgMinutes": 101}, "wake": {"count": 14, "minutes": 64, "thirtyDayAvgMinutes": 62}}}, {"logId": "5219582044173511000", "minutesAfterWakeup": 0, "minutesAsleep": 300, "minutesToFallAsleep": 0, "logType": "auto_detected", "timeInBed": 365, "type": "stages"}]
1	summary	{"totalMinutesAsleep": 300, "totalSleepRecords": 1, "totalTimeInBed": 365, "stages": {"deep": 49, "light": 207, "rem": 44, "wake": 64}}

```
1 {
2   "sleep": [
3     {
4       "dateOfSleep": "2025-12-25",
5       "duration": 21900000,
6       "efficiency": 82,
7       "startTime": "2025-12-24T23:04:00.000",
8       "endTime": "2025-12-25T05:09:00.000",
9       "infoCode": 0,
10      "isMainSleep": true,
11      "levels": { ...
123    },
124    "logId": 5219582044173511000,
125    "minutesAfterWakeup": 0,
126    "minutesAsleep": 65,
127    "minutesAsleep": 300,
128    "minutesToFallAsleep": 0,
129    "logType": "auto_detected",
130    "timeInBed": 365,
131    "type": "stages"
132  },
133 ],
134 "summary": {
135   "totalMinutesAsleep": 300,
136   "totalSleepRecords": 1,
137   "totalTimeInBed": 365,
138   "stages": {
139     "deep": 49,
140     "light": 207,
141     "rem": 44,
142     "wake": 64
143   }
144 }
145 }
```

Images of the sleep statistics are screenshots taken by the Author by applying filter: date: 12/25/2025.

All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsVfOy1KKGJ4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Fitbit Web API

ECG Logs ▼ Date:

#	timestamp	value
0	ecgReadings	[{"startTime": "2026-05-08T10:42:34.378", "averageHeartRate": 71, "resultClassification": "Normal Sinus Rhythm", "waveformSamples": [-6199, -6476, -6616, -6581, -6407, -6122, -5724, -5226, -4724, -4354, -4142, 2.17-2.26], "deviceName": "Charge 6", "firmwareVersion": "20001.220.31"}]
1	pagination	{"afterDate": "2026-05-08T00:00:00.000", "limit": 10, "next": "", "offset": 0}

```

1  {
2    "ecgReadings": [
3      {
4        "startTime": "2026-05-08T10:42:34.378",
5        "averageHeartRate": 71,
6        "resultClassification": "Normal Sinus Rhythm",
7        "waveformSamples": [ ...
7508      ],
7509      "samplingFrequencyHz": 250,
7510      "scalingFactor": 10922,
7511      "numberOfWaveformSamples": 7500,
7512      "leadNumber": 1,
7513      "featureVersion": "2.17-2.17-2.26",
7514      "deviceName": "Charge 6",
7515      "firmwareVersion": "20001.220.31"
7516    }
7517  ],
7518  "pagination": {
7519    "afterDate": "2026-05-08T00:00:00.000",
7520    "limit": 10,
7521    "next": "",
7522    "offset": 0,
7523    "previous": "",
7524    "sort": "ASC"
7525  }
7526 }

```

- Images of the ECG statistics are screenshots taken by the Author by applying filter: date: 05/08/2026.
- All materials are available on https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eiBsjopJunqrmGT7ECsVfOy1KGJ4BA79?usp=drive_link, accessed on 9. May 2026.

Fitbit Freedom: Raspberry Pi Local Server for Fitbit Data

Miloš Milošević, PhD student

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Let's talk!

- Do you recall the main limitations we encountered during the Fitbit Charge 6 overview?
- What kind of infrastructure would you recommend for hosting sensitive data?
- What was the key takeaway or most interesting part for you?

Fitbit Freedom: Raspberry Pi Local Server for Fitbit Data

Miloš Milošević, PhD student

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*Access to fine
grained Fitbit
data*

*PSSOH for Fitbit
data access*

*Infrastructure
for further
analysis*

Other wearables

Apple Watch

- ECG feature region-restricted
- HealthKit developer APIs
- No raw sensor access

<https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT208955>

Samsung Galaxy Watch

- Samsung Health Sensor SDK
- Access to HR, ECG, SpO₂
- Regional restrictions apply

<https://developer.samsung.com/health/sensor>

Garmin

- Garmin Health API available
- Access to activity metrics
- Heart rate and sleep data

<https://developer.garmin.com/gc-developer-program/health-api/>

Oura Ring

- Official cloud API
- Strong sleep analytics
- No direct device access

<https://developer.ouraring.com>

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Regional restrictions exist
across multiple wearable
ecosystems.

Access to raw sensors
data is often limited.

Most platforms rely on
cloud-based APIs, so
Raspberry Pi
implementation is
possible.